

Residents' Perception of Development Control Challenges in the Southwestern Region of Nigeria

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Abstract

Development control plays a significant role in the orderly growth and sustainable development of cities. This is dependent on the perception held by the residents of development control operations. This study examined residents' perception of development control activities in the cities of southwestern Nigeria. Data for this study were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data were obtained through questionnaire administration. A total of 1790 building owners and heads of households were selected out of 89476 in the four identified residential zones (high, medium, low, and planned residential schemes) in Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti, and Osogbo through a multi-stage sampling technique. A descriptive method of data analysis was adopted in this study. Findings reveal that the socioeconomic characteristics of residents vary based on residential locations and this determines the residents' level of understanding of the roles of development control agencies, as well as their satisfaction and compliance with planning regulations. The results from this study further show that residents' perceptions of the functions of development control agencies (3.90) and their level of satisfaction (3.93) were low. This was more pronounced in the high and medium residential densities as the residents' perception of the functions of development control activities in the zones were 2.73 and 3.48 respectively. Despite the differences in the residents' perception, the study established that lack of development/master plans (4.53), poor monitoring (4.28), political interference (4.27) and bribery and corruption are the major problems militating against the effectiveness of development control operations in the study area. The study therefore recommends that the planning agencies should embark on aggressive public education and enlightenment campaigns to sensitize residents on the activities of the planning agencies. Efforts should be made by the government to rid the planning agencies of corrupt elements and take the necessary steps to prepare the development plans to guide the growth and development of the cities.

Keywords: Development Control, Southwest Nigeria, Resident Perception

1 INTRODUCTION

Today the world is grappling with the effects of urbanization which is orchestrated by a combination of factors that include natural increase, rural-urban migration, technological advancement, and socio-economic transformation

(Adeyemi, 2016; Kio-Lawanson, Duru, John and Ee-bee, 2016). The increase in population in the cities naturally translates to a high rate of physical development. The remarkable population growth in these cities results in ever-increasing pressure on available space for different purposes. These include but are not restricted to, transportation, commercial, industrial, residential, institutional, and recreational land uses (Aribigbola 2008; Okwuashi & Ofem, 2012). The increased competition by land users for available space within cities causes indiscriminate land use. Where these are not controlled or regulated, the resultant effect is an unsightly look or city clutter (Itoro and Usen, 2023). Some problems evident in cities of developing nations include high insecurity rates, improper waste disposal, overburdened public infrastructure, urban decay, urban sprawl, and overcrowding. These problems have been partly attributed to inadequate physical planning implementation (Efobi and Anierobi, 2013; Okoro, 2014; Adeyemi, 2016).

According to Okpala (2009), effective urban planning and implementation are the antidotes to those continuing urban challenges in Anglophone countries of Africa. Therefore, for cities to function effectively there is a need for intervention in the urban land use system to achieve a certain goal of urban development that relates to public interest such as sustainability, health, safety, convenience, efficiency, energy conservation, environmental quality, social equity, and amenity. Urban planning relates to using land or the spatial expression of the desired form of social and economic development to be translated on the ground (Adeyemi and Onifade, 2019). Central to physical planning activities worldwide is the control of development, which is a strong and effective tool of urban planning and management (Efobi and Anierobi, 2013). According to Adeyemi *et. al* (2023), development control is the process of enforcing and implementing the approved planning standards in conformity with the provisions of urban

development plans. It is concerned with ensuring that the urban environment is organized and developed in an orderly manner to support robust health and sustainable development (Liman, 2020). Ibrahim and Emmanuel (2014) also see a development control system as a way to control the excesses of people concerning the development of urban land and the general environment by making sure that people obey the law or regulations governing the use and development of space.

Aluko (2004) identified three reasons for enforcing development control as follows: the need for effective development control is to prevent abuse and misuse of land and to ensure compatible uses of land as stipulated in the master plan; development control also ensures that real estate developers or owners of landed property use their lands and buildings in conformity with approved town planning schemes or master plans for the town; also because of negative externalities generated by some users of land such as industrial areas which generate heavy traffic or pollute the environment so much as to cause a decline in the value of adjacent land uses such as residential. To effectively implement development control, section 27 of the Nigerian Urban and Regional Planning Law No. 88 of 1992 provides for the establishment of a development control department at all levels of government (federal, state, and local). Based on the provision in section 28 of this law, no development is expected to take place without prior planning approval by the planning agencies. However, development control has been adopted at different levels of government in Nigeria for several decades to check the non-conforming land uses, but the operation seems to be confronted with several challenges. There are cases of incompatibility in various land uses both at the core and outer fringe of cities in Nigeria, thus raising a question about the level of effectiveness of physical planning and development control operations in the country.

Several commentators have however documented factors responsible for ineffectiveness in development control operations. For example, Ogundele, Ayo, Odewumi and Aigbe (2011) investigated challenges of development control in Festac Town, Lagos through the administration of questionnaires to the residents and the interview of development control officials. The study revealed such hindrances as lack of planning tools and equipment, inadequate funding of planning agencies, inadequacy of professionally qualified planners, ineffective development control procedure, lack of organized public enlightenment campaign, and above all, the acts of bribery and corruption among development control officers were responsible for ineffective development control operation. Similarly, Kio-Lawanson *et al.* (2016) examined challenges confronting development control in some selected cities in the Niger Delta region of the country. The study established that inadequate funding, lack of equipment and machinery, lack of adequate public enlightenment, corruption on

the part of planning officers, and political interference among others were some of the problems hindering effective development control in the capital cities. Osita (2019) in a study based in Oyo town documented the challenges facing development control under four groups public constraints, personal constraints, institutional constraints, and logistic constraints. The recommendation of this study which is from a professional perspective was that for effective development control that will meet emerging smart cities, a city that works, collective efforts of all the stakeholders involved are necessary. In another dimension, Odekunle, Adekunle, and Adebayo (2019) in their study based on Abeokuta confirmed that individual developers refused to submit their layout plans for approval hence leading to a disjointed layout.

A cursory look at studies on challenges reviewed above though valid reveals that solutions to the planning and development control problems most often are from the professional point of view with little effort being made to integrate the views of the people into the policy framework for environmental planning. Since all development control activities are planned for the welfare of the people, the need for their involvement becomes very fundamental (Efobi and Anierobi, 2013). According to Fakolade and Coblenz (1981), citizens are not mere receivers but suppliers and evaluators of information because they already have a large stock of "ordinary" knowledge that is relevant and necessary for their problem-solving. In essence, the citizen is the greatest resource for improving the process and output of planning and development control. Decisions reached through maximum public involvement are most likely to have minimum opposition, thus reducing friction, easing implementation, and avoiding expensive reversal of decisions. (Fakolade and Coblenz, 1981).

The contention that public policymaking remains incomplete without public participation is increasing rapidly in today's modern world (Ayodele and Abiodun, 2015). No doubt, we are currently in a democratic regime, where the common man is expected to have a voice in matters affecting local planning and development. This is in line with Sustainable Development Goal 11(3) of enhancing inclusive and sustainable urbanization and capacity for participatory, integrated, and sustainable human settlement planning and management. The Nigeria Urban and Regional Planning Law No 88 of 1992 in sections 13-26 further supports submissions from members of the public as input for the preparation of a development

guide. This further underscores the need to consider the perception of the members of the public as a necessary ingredient in addressing development control challenges. However, to achieve success in any physical planning activity, information about people's perception of physical development cannot be ignored.

The perception of one's capability according to Kaoje, Sabir, Yusuf, Jimoh, and Raji (2017) is said to set a limit to what to do and ultimately what can be achieved. It influences how a person views himself and the world around him and how it tends to govern his behavior. Studying the perception held of an issue by residents according to Afon (2007) has some advantages-how residents perceive an issue may produce a change of attitude, and promote pressure group and spirited participation. Perception reveals the image of everyday users of the city and indicate the existence of major problems, it also helps policymakers in identifying the need and direction to which public education and enlightenment campaign will focus. However, studies on perception of the development control challenges have been scanty. The few available include Afon (2009) which is limited in scope. Others include Agbonta and Olowoporoku (2017) and Usen (2023) which did not consider the view of residents across different residential zones that are occupied by people of different socioeconomic statuses. It is on this premise that this study seek to investigate the residents' perception of development control challenges across the different residential zones of cities in southwestern Nigeria.

2.1 THE STUDY AREA

Following the outcome of the sovereign national constitution between 1993 and 1996 which recommended for creation of regions, the federal government in 1997 made an official pronouncement of six geopolitical regions (North East, North Central, North West, South East, South-South and South West) to allay the fears of most of the major ethnic groups regarding adequate representation in the development process. The Southwestern region comprising Lagos, Oyo, Ogun, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti states is the area for this study. The region is located in the southern part of the country and shares boundaries with the Atlantic Ocean in the South, Kwara and Kogi States in the north, Edo State in the East, and the Republic of Benin in the West (see Figure 1). According to Nwaka (2005) the southwest is the

most urbanized region in Nigeria. The region covers a land mass of 78,505.166 square kilometers and is the second most populous (27,511,992) region after the northwest (35,786.944) (The National Population Commission, 2006). This study will be limited to the capital cities of Ogun (Abeokuta), Osun (Osogbo) and Ekiti (Ado-Ekiti).

Abeokuta became the capital city of Ogun and Abeokuta local Government in 1976. It lies between latitude $07^{\circ} 03'N$ and $07^{\circ} 15'$ and longitude $03^{\circ} 19'E$ and $03^{\circ} 25'E$. The city is about 81km southwest of Ibadan, the capital of Oyo State, and 106km North of Ikeja, the capital of Lagos. The first impetus to the growth of the town was the opening of the Lagos-Aro railine in 1898. The rail line reached Abeokuta in 1900, and a railway station was established in Lafenwa area of the city which put the town in a unique position, as it became a provincial headquarters, There are two major physical features, that have exerted a direct influence on the physical growth and development of the city. The first is the presence of Olumo Rock (172.8m) in the central part of the town. Abeokuta, meaning under the rock derives its name from Olumo rock which protects the people in the town from attack of the enemies. Since then Olumo Rock has been revered and worshiped by Egbas and serves as a major tourist site in the city. The second is the Ogun River located in the southwest part of the town passing the foot of Ajuwon hill. These physical features have given a unique pattern of landscape to the town and to some extent, have limited the physical growth and expansion of the town to the flatter and easily developing areas. What is regarded as Abeokuta today comprises Abeokuta South Local Government, Abeokuta North Local Government, Obafemi Owode Local Government, and Odeda Local Government respectively.

Osogbo is located about 95km northeast of Ibadan. Precisely Osogbo lies between latitude $07^{\circ} 47'N$ and $07^{\circ} 48'N$ and longitude $04^{\circ} 33'E$ and $04^{\circ} 37'E$. It covers areas of about 150 square kilometers and lies at a height of 366 meters above sea level (Adeyemi, 2016). According to Obateru (2006), the location of Osogbo is premised on two

important reasons. First, the founding of Osogbo authenticates the primary significance of water supplies to the establishment of Yoruba towns and cities. Second, Osogbo is believed to have been founded by Ijeshas as a military outpost to counter the military threat of the Alafin Kori who had established Ede as a war camp to arrest the activities of Ijesha marauders. Osogbo became the capital of Osun state following the creation of a new state out of the old Oyo state in 1991. What is regarded as Osogbo today comprises of Osogbo local government and Olorunda local government respectively. It is bounded by Ifelodun/Irepodun local government in the north, Edenorth and Iles West in the south, Obokun and Boriipe in the east, and shares a boundary with Orolu and Egbedore local governments in the west within a maximum radius of ²⁵km. There is a high level of interaction between Osogbo and the adjoining towns.

Ado-Ekiti is the cultural headquarters of Ekiti land, doubling as the seat of the Ado local government after it acquired the status of state capital on October 1st, 1996. Ado-Ekiti is located between latitude 07°3'N and 07° 49'N and longitude 05° 7'E and 05° 7'E of the Greenwich meridian. It is bounded by Irepodun Local Government in the north, in the west by Ekiti Southwest, in the east by Gboyin Local government and shares boundaries with Ikere, Ise/Orun, and Emure local government areas in the south. The city is a fast-growing urban centre and this has become more pronounced with the creation of Ekiti state. This was a result of the influx of people from various places into the city in search of better opportunities. The population of Ado-Ekiti based on the 2006 population estimate is 313,690. Statutorily the city has only one local government and is divided into 13 political wards.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

The six states in the Southwestern zone were stratified into three groups: Lagos/Ogun, Oyo/Osun, and On-Ekiti. The basis for this is that each group adopts a similar method of development control. For example, Lagos/Ogun states have Physical Planning Boards; Oyo/Osun states operate a Local Planning Authority system, while Ondo/Ekiti states centralize their planning activities in the Ministry. One state was selected randomly from each group. The three states selected for this study were Ogun, Osun and Ekiti. The focus of this study was the state capitals. Thus, the state capitals of Ogun, Ekiti, and Osun (Abeokuta, Ado

Ekiti and Osogbo) were selected. The state capitals were further stratified into four residential zones – core transition, suburban, and planning schemes. This study adopted a survey method and the unit of investigation was household. Data for the study were obtained directly from the 1790 residents from the four identified residential zones in each city through a systematic random sampling technique. The first sample in each of the residential zones was selected randomly and the subsequent selection of the 50th building along the line of movement. Using this method, a total of six hundred and eighty-one questionnaires were administered in Abeokuta (core 348; transition 216; suburban 89 and planning scheme 28); six hundred and seventy one in Osogbo (core 207; transition 260; suburban 150 and planning scheme 54) and four hundred and thirty-seven in Ado Ekiti (core 154; transition 165; suburban 89 and planning scheme 29) respectively. Using residential zones in primary data collection, according to Beyer Afon (2005), is said to be reliable because of the following features and consequently, its associated advantages: (i) urban residential zones tend to exhibit more permanent geographical features in terms of locations, structures, housing types, commercial activities amongst others; (ii) these permanent geographic features objectively represent the social, economic and cultural attributes of residents; (iii) each residential zone is likely to internally contain residents' that have homogenous social and economic characteristics and (iv) by grouping urban centre into residential zones, the analysis of who live in each, the perception and compliance to development control associated with each grouping is considerably simplified.

Information obtained includes socioeconomic, and perception of respondents on the expected functions and challenges of development control in the study area. The questionnaire was structured to elicit information on residents' level of agreement with the functions, satisfaction, and severity of the challenges facing development control operations in the study area. Residents were asked to rate each function on a seven-point Likert scale of very much in agreement (VMA) much in agreement (MA), Agree(A), Just in agreement (JA), disagree(D), much in disagreement (MD) and very much in disagreement (VMD). Each rating was assigned a weight value of 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2,

and 1 respectively. Similarly, the residents' satisfaction with functions of development control was measured based on a seven-point Likert scale of very much satisfied (VMS) = 7, very satisfied (VS) = 6, satisfied (S) = 5, just satisfied (JS) = 4, not satisfied (NS) = 3, not very satisfied (NA) = 2 and not very much satisfied (NVMS) = 1 respectively. The level of seriousness of the challenges of development control was measured using a 7-point Likert scale of very much serious (VMS) = 7, very serious (VS) = 6, serious (S) = 5, just serious (JS) = 4, not serious (NS) = 3, not very serious (NVS) = 2, and not very much serious (NVMS) = 1 respectively. The analysis led to the development of indexes known as Perceived Function Index (PFI), Residents Satisfaction Index (RSI), and Level of Seriousness Index (LSI) respectively.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria Showing the six Geopolitical Zones

Figure 2: Map of South West Showing Selected States

Source of fig 1 & 2: Cooperative Information Network (COPINE), OAU, Ile-Ife 2023

3. Discussion of Findings

3.1 Socio-economic Characteristics of Residents in the Study Area

The socio-economic characteristics considered were education, income, and length of stay. These variables are significant in determining residents' housing choice location, perception, and compliance with development control regulations.

An evaluation of respondents' age presented in Table 1 shows that more than half (56.9%) of the respondents in the study area were within the active working age bracket of 31-60 years. Of 1019 in this category in the study area, 43.5%, 59.0%, and 72.2% resided in high, medium, and low densities respectively, while the planning scheme occupied 70.3%. It is instructive to note that the high density accommodated the largest share of respondents whose ages were above 60 years. The proportions of the aged residing in the medium and low densities were 39.4% and 24.5%, while it accounted for 41.5% in the planned residential scheme. The study further revealed that the population's age decreased as distance increased from high density to low density. It can be deduced based on this finding that a high number of the aged were accommodated in the high-density area may to a large extent determine the type of activities they engage in, the environmental quality, perception, and compliance with development control regulation.

Educational status is regarded as one of the major variables that determine residents' level of awareness, perception, and compliance with development control regulations (Afon 2006, 2009; Gbakeji and Rilwan 2009). For ease of analysis, the educational backgrounds of respondents were categorized into four. These were respondents with no formal education, primary, secondary or tertiary educational background (see Table 2). In the study area (Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti, and Osogbo), 75.9% had formal education, while 22.8% were without formal education. It is revealed from the analysis that the high density not only harbored the highest number of illiterates (43.3%), but it was also occupied by the highest proportions of respondents with primary school background (15.0%) and secondary (21.7%). The proportions of respondents with tertiary education in each residential density were 15.6%, 52.0%, 68.8% and 90.4% respectively in the high, medium,

and low densities and planned residential schemes. The proportions of respondents that were without formal education, primary and secondary were highest in the high density. These were on the reduction as distance increases from high to low density. On the other hand, the proportion of respondents with tertiary education was least in the high density and this was on the increase as distance increased from high density to low. If the finding by Afon (2006) is anything to go by, that respondents' level of awareness increases with the increase in the level of education, the respondents' level of awareness of development control activities will vary directly with increased distance from the high to low density residential areas. The above assertion is confirmed by the result of the Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 510.641$; $p = 0.000$) indicate there was a significant difference in respondents' educational status among residential densities in the study area.

Respondents' income was grouped into four based on the government-approved salary grade level/structure. The first group was respondents below grade level 01 (those who earned below the government-approved minimum wage of N18000 per month). The second group of income earners were those on levels 01-06, while the third and fourth respectively were those on levels 07- 12 and 13 - 17. These were respectively referred to as below-poverty line, low, medium, and high-income groups. From the analysis above, the majority of the respondents in the study area could be categorized as middle-income earners. This income group represented 42.6% in the three cities. The highest number of respondents in the middle-income bracket resided in the medium density. It was established that 54.0% of the middle-income earners occupied the medium density. However, the proportion of respondents in the same income category in the high, and low densities and planning scheme were 30.6% 45.2% and 40.0% respectively. Findings further showed that the proportion of the respondents who lived below the poverty line and those in the low-income category was highest (14.2% and 48.2% respectively) in the high-density, while those in the middle-income and high-income groups were the highest (53.6%) in the medium density and (46.7%) in the planned residential scheme respectively. The pattern of distribution as shown in Figure 3 was that the proportions of respondents who lived below the poverty line and those who were in the low-income category were on the decrease as distance increased from high to low densities. On the other hand, the proportion of high-income earners reduced with distance from high to low densities. The mean monthly income for

the three cities was N48887.52, while the mean monthly income in the high, medium, and low densities and planned residential scheme were N31051.86, N52632, N64659, and N78210.52 respectively. It hereby concluded that the mean monthly income for high density was less than the mean monthly income for the study area. The result of ANOVA ($F = 87.509$; $p = 0.000$) established a significant difference in respondents' income across the different residential locations of the study area.

Figure 3: Income Status of Respondents in the Study Area.

Source: Authors' field survey

The numbers of years spent by the respondents in the different residential locations were grouped into four as 1 to 10 years, 11 to 20 years, 21 to 30 years and above 30 years as contained in Table 4. This variable is very important because it will influence the respondent's experience on development control activities. It was established that variation exists in the respondents' length of stay across the different residential densities of cities in the study area. The analysis in Figure 4 below confirms this. The proportion of respondents who had stayed between 1 and 10 years was highest in the low density, those who had stayed between 11 to 20 years was highest in the planned residential scheme and the proportion of respondents who had stayed between 21 and 30 years and above 30 years respectively in their residential locations were highest in the high density. The pattern of distribution was that the proportions of respondents who stayed between 1 and 10 years 11 and 20 years in their respective locations increased as distance increased from the high to low densities. On the other hand, the proportion of respondents who had lived between 21 and 30 years and above 30 years in their respective residential locations reduced as distance increased from high to low densities respectively. The mean

length of stay of household heads in the high, medium, and low densities and planned residential schemes were 29.20, 19.78, 14.30, and 13.54, while the mean of stay of household heads for the three cities was 21.62. It can therefore be concluded that the respondents in the high density had the longest stay and this decreased as distance increased from high to low densities. The result of ANOVA ($F = 169.054$; $p = 0.000$) further confirms the variation in the respondents' length of stay in the different residential densities of cities in the Southwestern Region.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Residents in the Different Residential Areas

Age (in Years)	Abokuta				Oshogbo				Ado-Ekiti				Study Area				Total			
	High	Medi-um	Low	Sche mes	To-tal	High	Medi-um	Low	Sche mes	To-tal	High	Medi-um	Low	Sche mes	To-tal					
19-30	0 (0.0)	1 (0.5)	2 (1.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (0.4)	2 (1.0)	6 (2.3)	9 (6.0)	2 (3.7)	19 (2.8)	2 (1.3)	3 (1.8)	2 (2.2)	0 (0.0)	7 (1.6)	4 (0.6)	10 (1.6)	13 (3.3)	2 (1.8)	29 (1.6)
31-60	132 (45.8)	126 (58.3)	96 (11.5)	14 (50.0)	368 (54.0)	122 (58.9)	164 (63.1)	109 (72.0)	46 (85.2)	441 (65.0)	28 (18.0)	88 (53.3)	76 (85.0)	18 (62.1)	210 (48.0)	282 (43.5)	378 (59.0)	281 (72.2)	78 (70.3)	1019 (56.9)
> 60	8 (2.7)	89 (41.2)	3 (1.0)	14 (50.0)	0 (0.0)	83 (40.1)	90 (34.6)	7 (2.6)	6 (11.1)	7 (31.0)	2 (8.0)	74 (44.8)	4 (12.0)	11 (37.9)	1 (50.0)	363 (55.9)	253 (39.4)	95 (24.5)	31 (27.9)	742 (41.5)
Total	288 (42.2)	216 (31.7)	150 (22.0)	28 (04.1)	682 (100)	207 (30.8)	260 (38.7)	150 (22.0)	54 (8.1)	671 (100)	154 (35.0)	165 (37.8)	89 (20.0)	29 (6.6)	437 (100)	649 (100.0)	641 (100.0)	389 (100.0)	111 (100.0)	1790 (100.0)

Source: Authors' Field Survey updated, 2023

Table 3: Respondents' Income Status in the Different Residential Areas

In- come Level	Abeokuta					Ado-Ekiti					Osogbo					Study Area				
	High	Medi- um	Low	Sche mes	Total	High	Medi- um	Low	Sche mes	Total	High	Medi- um	Low	Sche mes	Total	High	Medi- um	Low	Sche mes	Total
Level Below	31	5	6	0	42	29	7	2	1	39	29	13	6	0	48	89	25	14	1	129
Level 01	(11.0)	(2.4)	(4.2)	(0.0)	(6.2)	(19.5)	(4.4)	(2.3)	(3.6)	(9.3)	(14.8)	(5.1)	(4.1)	(0.0)	(7.4)	(14.2)	(4.0)	(3.7)	(0.9)	(7.5)
01-06	150	50	18	1	219	54	19	9	6	88	98	34	26	6	164	302	103	53	13	471
	(52.1)	(23.7)	(12.7)	(4.2)	(32.1)	(36.2)	(12.0)	(10.5)	(21.4)	(20.9)	(50.0)	(13.2)	(17.8)	(11.3)	(25.1)	(48.2)	(16.4)	(14.2)	(12.4)	(27.2)
07-12	93	121	83	9	306	56	81	38	7	182	43	134	48	26	251	192	336	169	42	739
> 12	(32.3)	(57.3)	(58.5)	(37.5)	(44.8)	(37.6)	(51.3)	(44.2)	(25.0)	(43.2)	(21.9)	(51.9)	(32.9)	(49.1)	(38.4)	(30.6)	(53.6)	(45.2)	(40.0)	(42.6)
Total	8	35	35	14	92	10	51	37	14	112	26	77	66	21	190	44	163	138	49	394
	(2.8)	(16.6)	(24.6)	(58.3)	(13.5)	(6.7)	(32.3)	(43.0)	(50.0)	(26.6)	(13.3)	(29.8)	(45.2)	(38.6)	(29.1)	(26.0)	(36.9)	(46.7)	(1733)	(22.7)
	282	211	142	24	659	149	158	86	28	421	196	258	146	53	653	627	627	374	105	1733
	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(3.4)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(7.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)

Source: Author's Field Survey updated, 2023

Table 4: Respondents' Length of Stay in the Different Residential Areas

Length of Stay	Abeokuta					Ado-Ekiti					Osogbo					Study Area				
	High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total	High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total	High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total	High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total
	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)	Fre. (%)
1-10	8 (2.8)	14 (6.5)	60 (40.0)	6 (22.2)	88 (12.9)	4 (2.6)	43 (26.1)	40 (44.9)	12 (42.8)	99 (22.7)	14 (6.8)	56 (21.5)	69 (49.0)	29 (53.7)	168 (25.1)	26 (4.0)	113 (17.7)	169 (43.4)	47 (43.1)	355 (19.9)
11-20		43 (20.3)	47 (31.3)	16 (59.3)	137 (20.2)	20 (13.0)	75 (45.5)	42 (47.2)	8 (28.6)	145 (33.3)	53 (25.7)	137 (52.2)	61 (40.7)	22 (40.7)	273 (40.8)	104 (39.8)	255 (38.6)	150 (38.6)	46 (42.2)	555 (31.1)
21-30	31 (10.8)	0	0	3 (3)	141 (20.7)	60 (39.0)	32 (19.4)	6 (6.7)	8 (28.6)	106 (24.3)	7 (3.7)	0	13 (8.7)	3 (5.6)	143 (21.3)	0	140 (21.9)	43 (11.1)	16 (14.7)	390 (21.8)
>30	54 (18.7)	58 (27.0)	24 (16.0)	5 (28.6)	20 (28.7)	39 (70.0)	19 (4.1)	0	0	24.3 (0.0)	77 (37.4)	50 (19.2)	0	0	86 (12.3)	191 (50.6)	132 (20.6)	27 (6.9)	0 (0.0)	486 (27.7)
Total	195 (67.7)	100 (46.5)	190 (12.7)	0 (0.0)	314 (46.2)	70 (45.5)	15 (9.1)	1 (1.1)	0 (0.0)	86 (19.7)	62 (30.1)	17 (6.5)	7 (4.7)	54 (100.0)	86 (100.0)	191 (327.0)	132 (206.0)	27 (150.0)	0 (0.0)	486 (100.0)

Author's Field Survey updated, 2023

Figure 4: Respondent length of Stay in the Different Residential Area of the Study Area

3.2 Residents' Perception of the Functions of Development Control Agencies

3.2.1 Residents Perception of Functions of Development Control Agencies in Abeokuta

The functions that development control agencies are expected to perform were investigated. The understanding of these functions based on residents' perception varied across the different residential densities in the study area. From the result presented in Table 5, the mean of the Perceived Function Index (\overline{PFI}) for Abeokuta was 4.04, while \overline{PFI} for the high, medium, and low densities and planned residential schemes were 2.78, 3.64, 4.67, and 4.79 respectively. This pattern suggests that the level of understanding of the functions development control agencies can perform increased as distance increases from high to low densities. A situation that had something to do with changes in socio-economic attributes of residents most especially income and education. It can therefore be stated that the respondents' level of compliance could follow the pattern of residents' perception in the city. Further analysis showed that despite the low level of perception expressed by respondents in the high residential density, nine functions have indices higher than 2.78. Some of these are declaring some roads as one-way traffic (4.11), the location of solid waste storage cans (3.96) and the selection of solid waste disposal sites (3.79). On the other hand, while the respondents expect planning agencies to perform functions that will improve the quality of the physical environment, they did not want their right to develop their land to be curtailed. This was why the least important function of development control agencies as perceived by the respondents in the zone was granting planning permits (1.61). Other functions with negative deviations about the mean of PFI were the preparation of physical development plans and the selection of sites for different land uses with an index of 1.71 each.

With \overline{PFI} of 3.64 in the medium residential density, thirteen functions had positive deviations. This includes the location of solid waste storage cans (4.15), opening up of roads (3.94), and granting of fence permit and the selection of solid waste collection points with an index of 3.92 each respectively. The residents in the low residential density had a better understanding of functions development control agencies can perform. With an index of 4.79 in the zone, twelve functions had indices

higher than the \overline{PFI} . The most important of these was the granting of a planning permit to the proposed development (6.16). Other functions with indices higher than the average in the order of importance were granting of fence permit (5.94), preparation of residential layout (5.86), selection of a site for different uses (5.66), and selection and design of functional open spaces (5.63).

Similarly in the planned residential scheme, eleven of the identified functions of development control agencies had positive deviations around \overline{PFI} (4.67). The activity with the highest level of agreement was the granting of a planning permit (5.56). In Abeokuta, it is established that not only there were variations in the perceptions of functions development control agencies were expected to perform, but the understanding of these functions by the residents also varied across the different residential densities of Abeokuta. Despite the differences, thirteen of the identified functions had indices higher than the mean index for the city (4.04). These include the location of the solid waste storage tank (4.42), granting of fence permit (4.29), granting of planning permit (4.26), formulation of physical development policies (4.26), and selection of solid waste collection point (4.22).

3.2.2 Residents' Perception of Functions of Development Control Agencies in Ado-Ekiti

The \overline{PFI} for Ado-Ekiti was 4.04, while the mean of PFI for high, medium, and low densities and planned residential schemes were 2.70, 3.92, 4.72, and 5.02. This pattern suggests that the respondents' level of understanding of functions development control agencies can perform increased as distance increases from high to low densities.

In the high-density, eleven of these functions had indices higher than the mean of PFI for the zone. The most important of these functions were involvement in economic development at the local level, location of solid waste storage cans, and selection of solid waste collection points and monitoring with an index of 3.68 each respectively. The high preference for the location of solid waste storage cans is a result of poor environmental conditions in the core residential area of the cities. To compound this, the waste storage receptacles were not provided in strategic

locations by the appropriate agencies which made the residents dump waste indiscriminately along the roads in the city. Other functions as perceived by respondents in the zone include settlement of disputes in land use development (3.54) and location of solid waste disposal site (3.50).

From Table 5, development control agencies are expected to perform nine important functions in the medium density of Ado-Ekiti. This is because each of these functions had an index higher than the mean of PFI(3.93) for the zone. The most important of these functions were granting planning permits (4.58), preparation of development plans (4.46), formulations of physical development policies (4.23), controlling physical development activities (4.20), and the preparation of residential layouts (4.04). The remaining ten functions had indices below the mean of PFI.

With \overline{PFI} of 4.72 in the low density, the most important function development control agencies are expected to perform is granting planning permits (5.88). Other functions in the order of importance were the preparation of a development plan (5.63), formulation of physical development policies (5.48), selection of sites for different land uses (5.33), controlling of physical development activities (5.31), and preparation of residential layout (5.30).

It is to be noted that planning schemes are government-controlled housing estates. No Individual is permitted to build any structure without a valid allocation. This could be the reason why granting of planning permit (6.18) was most favored by the respondents in the planned residential scheme of Ado Ekiti. Other functions with indices higher than the mean index (5.02) for the zone based on residents' perception were the formulation of physical development policies (6.08), preparation of development plans (5.97) control of physical development activities (5.79), preparation of residential layout (5.72), selection of a site for different use (5.45) and selection and designing of functional open spaces.

It is confirmed from the findings in Table 5 that the magnitude of the respondent's level of agreement with functions that development control agencies are expected to perform increased as distance increases from the high to low density in Ado-Ekiti. While the mean PFI for the city was 4.04, it represented 2.70,

3.92, 4.72 and 5.02 in the high, medium, and low densities and planned residential schemes respectively. This is an indication that the socioeconomic characteristics of respondents influenced the perception of the functions of development agencies. With an index of 4.04 for the city of Ado-Ekiti, thirteen of the identified functions of development control agencies had positive deviations from the \overline{PFI} .

Some of these were the granting of planning permits (4.51), formulation of physical development policies (4.47), preparation of physical development plans (4.45), preparation of residential layout (4.25), and the selection and designing of functional open space (4.18).

3.2.3 Residents Perception of Functions of Development Control Agencies in Osogbo

It can be seen From Table 5, that Perceived

Function Index (\overline{PFI}) for Osogbo was 3.62, while the mean of PFI for high, medium and low densities and planned residential schemes were 2.71, 2.89, 3.39 and 5.47 respectively.

With an index of 2.71 in the high residential zone, development control agencies are expected to perform fourteen important functions. This is because each of the functions had an index higher than the mean of PFI for the zone. The most important of these functions was the settlement of disputes on land use development (3.00). Other functions expected of development control agencies include the location of bus stops (2.90), the location of solid waste storage cans (2.89), taking part in street naming (2.86), and involvement in economic development at the local level (2.82).

In the medium density of Osogbo, the most important functions of development control agencies as perceived by the respondents include the location of the bus stop (3.31), declaring some roads as one-way traffic (3.30) and settlement of disputes in land use development (3.19). Others were taking part in street naming (3.12) and the selection of solid waste disposal sites (3.10). The perceptions of the respondents in the zone typified the prevailing situation in the city. There were no bus stops along the major roads where vehicles could load and unload. This contribute to traffic congestion experienced along Gbongan – Orita Olaiya – Ikirun, and Okefia-

Alekuwodo road. It is instructive to note that the prevailing situations in the various residential densities to a large extent influence respondents' perceptions of the functions development control agencies expected to perform.

With an index of 3.39 in the low density, three of the functions planning agencies had positive deviations from the mean of PFI. These were the formulation of physical development policies (5.77), granting of fence permits (3.80) and selection of solid waste collection points and monitoring (3.47).

The respondents in the planned residential density of Osogbo expressed the highest level of agreement with the functions of development control agencies. This was because the \overline{PFI} for the zone was 5.47. Based on this, eight of the identified activities of the development of control agencies had indices higher than the average mean for the zone. These were granting of planning permit (6.46), preparation of development plans (6.09), taking part in street naming, (5.79), and formulation of physical development policies (5.77). Others were controlling physical development activities (5.61), granting fence permits, location of bus stops (5.60), and preparation of residential layout (5.48).

Table 5: Residents' Perception of the Functions of Development Control Agencies in Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti and Osogbo

S / N	Perceived functions	Abeokuta					Ado-Ekiti					Osogbo					Study area
		High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total	High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total	High	Medium	Low	Schemes	Total	
		PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	PFI	
1	Granting of planning permit	1.61	3.69	6.16	5.56	4.26	1.39	4.58	5.88	6.18	4.51	2.33	2.16	3.29	6.46	3.56	4.11
2	Preparation of development plan	1.71	3.50	3.37	5.54	3.53	1.75	4.46	5.63	5.97	4.45	2.28	2.43	3.34	6.09	3.54	3.84
3	Formulation of physical development poli-	1.89	3.68	5.19	5.54	4.26	2.07	4.23	5.48	6.08	4.47	2.44	3.05	5.77	5.77	4.26	4.33
4	Controlling physical development activities	1.79	3.54	3.59	4.04	3.24	1.28	4.20	5.31	5.79	4.15	2.58	2.71	3.29	5.61	3.55	3.65
5	Preparation of residential layout	2.07	3.45	5.86	5.06	4.11	1.96	4.04	5.30	5.71	4.25	2.71	2.67	3.08	5.48	3.49	3.95
6	Selection of sites for different land use	1.71	3.68	5.66	5.15	4.05	1.75	3.97	5.33	5.45	4.13	2.70	2.93	3.17	5.36	3.54	3.91
7	Selection and design of functional open spaces	2.11	3.81	5.63	4.08	4.11	2.25	3.78	5.25	5.42	4.18	2.72	2.70	3.21	5.06	3.42	3.90
8	Opening up of roads	2.32	3.94	5.47	4.91	4.16	2.89	3.70	4.96	5.02	4.14	2.65	2.78	3.26	5.33	3.51	3.94
9	Granting of a fence permit	2.43	3.92	5.94	4.87	4.29	2.32	3.76	3.19	5.38	3.66	2.70	2.96	3.80	5.65	3.78	3.91
10	Settlement of dispute on land ownership	2.25	3.69	5.46	4.85	4.06	2.96	3.82	4.88	5.03	4.17	2.77	2.98	3.32	5.02	3.52	3.92
11	Involvement in economic development at the local level	2.79	3.82	5.22	4.68	4.13	3.68	3.76	4.82	4.83	4.27	2.82	2.95	3.25	5.06	3.52	3.97
12	Taking part in street naming	3.61	3.07	5.12	4.55	4.09	3.25	3.83	4.36	4.21	3.92	2.86	3.12	3.37	5.79	3.77	3.93
13	The location of solid waste storage can	3.96	4.15	4.73	4.38	4.42	3.68	3.61	4.06	3.96	3.26	2.89	2.73	2.39	5.28	3.32	3.66
14	Selection of solid waste collection point	4.11	3.92	4.69	4.16	4.22	3.68	3.54	3.73	3.96	3.25	2.75	2.78	3.47	5.46	3.62	3.70
15	Selection of solid waste disposal site	3.79	3.91	4.61	4.14	4.11	3.50	3.54	2.70	4.00	3.44	2.81	3.10	3.13	5.27	3.58	3.71
16	Settlement of dispute on land use development	3.50	3.78	4.84	4.26	4.10	3.54	3.95	4.92	4.62	4.26	3.00	3.19	3.29	5.16	3.66	4.01
17	Location of bus stops	3.61	3.72	4.85	4.31	4.12	3.25	3.89	4.75	4.82	4.18	2.90	3.31	3.37	5.60	3.80	4.03
18	Declaring city section special planning areas	3.46	3.80	4.74	4.11	4.03	2.86	3.99	4.90	4.97	4.18	2.76	3.05	3.18	5.40	3.60	3.94
19	Declaring some roads as one-way traffic	4.11	2.11	4.07	3.77	3.51	3.21	4.00	4.27	3.98	3.87	2.78	3.30	3.43	5.17	3.67	3.68
	Total	52.83	69.18	91.07	88.76	76.80	51.27	74.65	89.72	95.38	76.74	51.45	54.90	64.41	104.02	68.71	74.09
	PFI	2.78	3.64	4.79	4.67	4.47	2.70	3.92	4.72	5.02	4.04	2.71	2.89	3.39	5.47	3.61	3.90

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With a mean index of 3.61, respondents' perception of functions development control agencies can perform in Osogbo was between disagreed and just in agreement. This indicated that respondents' level of understanding of the functions of development control agencies was low. Despite the low level of agreement, six important functions were perceived in the city. These include the location of the bus stop (3.80), granting of a fence permit (3.78), and taking part in street naming (3.77). Others were declaring some roads as one-way traffic (3.67) and settlement of disputes in land use development (3.66).

3.2.4 Residents Perception of Functions of Development Control Agencies in Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti and Osogbo

The computed \overline{PFI} for the three cities was 3.90, while the index for Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti, and Osogbo were 4.04, 4.04, and 3.62 respectively. This indicated that respondents' level of agreement with the function of development control agencies was closer to just in agreement than disagreed. Although the result show that thirteen functions of the agencies had indices higher than the mean index for the study area, none of them had positive deviations across all the residential densities in the study area. This indicates that the perception of residents regarding the functions of development control agencies differ. However, the most important functions in the order of magnitude include formulation of physical development policies, granting of planning permits, location of bus stops, settlement of disputes in land use development, and involvement in economic development at the local level. Their respective indices were 4.33, 4.11, 4.03, 4.01, and 3.97 respectively.

3.3 Residents' Level of Satisfaction with the Activities of Development Control Agencies

The level of satisfaction respondents derived from the various functions of development control agencies in the three cities was investigated. This was measured through the Residents Satisfaction Index (RSI) and the result is presented in Table 6. The closer the RSI to seven the higher the resident's level of satisfaction.

3.3.1 Residents' Satisfaction with the Activities of Development Control Agencies in Abeokuta

The result of residents' satisfaction with the functions of development control agencies in the different residential densities of Abeokuta is presented in Table 6. Findings reveal that respondents in the high residential density of Abeokuta expressed a high level of satisfaction. With a Residents Satisfaction mean Index of 4.72 in the zone, the

respondents were satisfied with six of the functions of development control agencies. These include enforcement of development control regulations (5.12), settlement of disputes in land ownership (5.00), timely detection of contraventions (4.95), and education and enlightenment campaigns (4.79). The satisfaction level of residents can not be divorced from the program initiated by the past administration in the state termed 'homeowner charter' which gives owners of buildings with no valid documents to regularize same at a reduced cost and title documents will be issued.

In the medium density, respondents were satisfied with the four functions of development control agencies. This is because each of the four activities had an RSI higher than the mean (5.33) for the zone. The function that residents were satisfied with most was the settlement of disputes in land ownership (6.56). Other functions on which respondents expressed a high level of satisfaction include enforcement of development control regulation (5.46), timely detection of contravention (5.43), and dissemination and making available of planning information (5.36). On the other hand, each of the remaining seven activities of development control agencies had an index below the average mean of RSI for the zone. Despite the negative deviations of these activities from the mean of RSI, the residents' perceptions were between satisfied and much satisfied. These were education and enlightenment programs, public involvement in decision-making, and the period of granting planning approval. Their respective RSI were 5.32, 5.17, and 5.16 respectively.

Contrary to what was established in the high and medium densities, the function of planning agencies with positive deviations from the mean of RSI (3.77) in the low density were time lag before a decision is taken (3.95), timely communication of planning decision to residents (3.90), education and enlightenment program (3.82), the period of granting planning approval to proposed development (3.81) and timely action on contravention (3.79).

It was established that the respondents in the planned residential scheme expressed the least level of satisfaction. The mean index of 2.46 in the zone reveals that respondents' level of satisfaction was close to much dissatisfied than dissatisfied. The low level of satisfaction expressed by the respondents with the activities of development control did not indicate that the physical environmental condition in the zone was very

poor. Rather the educational status of respondents in the zone could have influenced their value judgment. Further analysis however revealed that five of the nine identified functions of planning agencies had positive deviations from the mean of RSI for the zone. These functions were settlement of disputes in land ownership, education and enlightenment campaigns, time lag before a decision is taken, and politeness of development control officers with an index of 2.75 each respectively.

From the Table, the \overline{RSI} for the city was 4.07, while the mean of RSI for the high, medium, and low residential densities and planned residential schemes were 4.73, 5.34, 3.77 and 2.46 respectively. This indicated that the residents' level of satisfaction with the function of planning agencies was higher in the high and medium densities than the low residential density and planned residential schemes respectively. However, the functions of development control agencies on which respondents derived substantial satisfaction in Abeokuta include settlement of disputes in land ownership (4.57), enforcement of development control regulations (4.14), public education and enlightenment campaign (4.13), timely detection of contraventions (4.09) and time lag before a decision is taken (4.08).

3.3.2 Residents' Satisfactions with the Functions of Development Control Agencies in Ado-Ekiti

With the resident satisfaction index (\overline{RSI}) of 3.85 for the high density of Ado-Ekiti, it can be established that six of the eleven identified functions of development control agencies had indices higher than the average for the zone. The functions on which respondents derived the highest level of satisfaction were timely detection of contravention and timely action on contravention. Each of these had an index of 4.18 respectively. Others were politeness of development control officers (4.05), the period of granting planning approval to proposed development (4.02), dissemination and making available of planning information (3.94), and settlement of dispute in land ownership (3.88).

In the medium density, the respondents' level of satisfaction was high. This is because the mean of RSI for the residential zone was 5.18 which indicates that the residents' satisfaction was between satisfied and much satisfied. Further analysis revealed that functions with negative deviations also had higher indices.

This can not be divorced from the activities of the government embarking on some projects to improve and bring about a facelift to the city being a state capital.

The mean of RSI for the low density was 4.85 indicating that respondents' satisfaction was close to satisfied than just satisfied. Based on this, respondents were satisfied with eight of the activities of development control agencies. This is because their respective deviations were above the mean of RSI for the zone. On the other hand, activities like settlement of disputes on land matters (2.86), time lag before a decision is taken (3.11) and public involvement in decision-making (4.49) enjoyed low levels of satisfaction by the respondents.

The respondents in the planned residential scheme expressed the least level of satisfaction with the activities of development control agencies in Ado-Ekiti. The mean of RSI for the zone was 2.89 which put the respondents' satisfaction between much dissatisfied and not satisfied. Apart from the GRA and Oke-Ila Housing Estate, developments in other housing estates in the Ado-Ekiti were still ongoing. For instance, none of the roads within the Elemi and Omisanjana housing estates were tarred. This could be responsible for the low level of satisfaction by the respondents in the zone. The functions of development control agencies on which respondents expressed a low level of satisfaction include enforcement of development control regulations (2.25), timely action on contraventions (2.43), and politeness of development control officers (2.64).

It is confirmed that residents in the high density (3.85) and the planned residential schemes (2.89) were less satisfied. This is because the mean indices

for the two residential zones were lower than \overline{RSI} for the city (4.07). Further analysis showed that the function of the development control agency on which respondents in the city derived the highest level of satisfaction was the period of granting planning approval to proposed development plans (4.48). Other important activities were the timely detection of contraventions (4.39), dissemination and making available of planning information (4.36), timely action on contravention (4.31) and politeness of development control officers (4.31). The respondent's level of satisfaction with each of the remaining five functions of the control agencies was below average.

3.3.3 Residents' Level of Satisfaction with Functions of Development Control Agencies in Osogbo

Investigation into the respondents' level of satisfaction with development control activities in Osogbo showed that high density had the lowest level of satisfaction. This is because the mean of RSI for the zone was 2.58 which put the perceptions between much dissatisfied and dissatisfied. Despite the low level of satisfaction, five of the functions of development control agencies in the zone had positive deviations about the mean of RSI. These functions include time lag before a decision is taken (2.75), timely communication of planning decisions to developers (2.72), education and enlightenment program (2.68), settlement of disputes in land ownership (2.63) and public involvement in decision-making (2.58). Each of the remaining six activities had negative deviations from the mean of RSI.

In the medium density, respondents were satisfied with eight of the functions of development control agencies in the zone. This was because each of these activities had an RSI higher than the mean index for the zone (2.79). The activities on which respondents expressed the highest level of satisfaction were the period of granting planning approval to development proposals and timely communication of planning decisions to developers with an index of 2.92 each respectively. It is to be noted therefore that despite the positive deviations from the mean of RSI, perceptions of these functions were between much dissatisfied and dissatisfied. The implication of this was that the respondent's level of satisfaction was low in the zone.

In the low density, the only function of development control agencies with RSI higher than the average mean of RSI was the politeness of the development control officer to developers (5.25). Each of the remaining ten of the functions identified had indices below the average mean.

Contrary to what was established in the traditional areas in Osogbo, respondents in the planned residential scheme expressed the highest level of satisfaction. The average mean of RSI for the zone was 5.25 which put the perception between satisfied and very satisfied. Going by this, five of the functions of development control agencies had indices above the mean of RSI. These functions were timely detection of contravention (6.19), dissemination and making available of planning of information (5.49), education and en-

lightenment campaign (5.29), enforcement of development control regulation (5.25), and politeness of development control officers (5.25). It is pertinent to note that development control activities in the planned residential scheme were being handled by separate agencies set up for that purpose. In essence, development plans were prepared to guide development activities within the scheme. This could be responsible for why respondents in the zone expressed the highest level of satisfaction.

From the Table 5, the \overline{RSI} for Osogbo was 3.53, while the index for the high, medium and low densities and planned residential schemes were 2.58, 2.79, 3.46 and 5.25 respectively. It is revealed from these figures that respondents' level of satisfaction increased as distance increased from the high to low densities. Further analysis showed that except in the planned residential scheme in the city, respondent level of satisfaction was low across the different residential densities. The result in the Table further confirms this assertion as only two of the functions of development control agencies had positive deviations about the mean of RSI. These were the timely detection of contravention (3.73) and politeness of development control officers (3.97). Each of the remaining nine activities had negative deviations from the mean of RSI. This implied that respondents were not in any way satisfied with the activities of development control agencies in the city.

Table 6: Residents' Satisfaction with Activities of the Development Control Agency in Abeokuta, Ado – Ekiti and Osogbo

S / N	Activities of Agency	Abeokuta					Ado-Ekiti					Osogbo					Study Area Total
		Hig h	Me diu m	Lo w	Sch eme s	To tal	Hi gh	Me- diu m	Lo w	Sch eme s	To- tal	High	Me- diu m	Lo w	Sc he me s	To tal	
1	Timely detection of contra- vention	4.9	5.4	3.7	2.2	4.0	4.1	5.3	5.6	2.4	4.3	2.57	2.7	3.4	6.1	3.7	4.07
2	Enforcement of develop- ment control regulations	5.1	5.4	3.7	2.2	4.1	3.3	5.3	5.4	2.2	4.1	2.55	2.6	3.3	5.2	3.4	3.90
3	Dissemination and making available planning infor- mation	4.3	5.3	3.6	2.5	3.9	3.9	5.1	5.5	2.7	4.3	2.43	2.5	3.4	5.4	3.4	3.94
4	Settlement of dispute in land ownership	5.0	6.5	3.7	2.7	4.5	3.8	5.2	2.8	2.8	3.7	2.63	2.6	3.1	4.9	3.3	3.85
5	Education and enlighten- ment program	4.7	5.3	3.8	2.7	4.1	3.7	5.0	5.0	3.0	4.2	2.68	2.8	3.3	5.2	3.5	3.97
6	Public involvement in deci- sion-making	4.7	5.1	3.6	2.2	3.9	3.8	5.0	4.4	3.2	4.1	2.58	2.8	3.1	4.9	3.4	3.84
7	Period of approving devel- opment proposals	4.7	5.1	3.8	2.2	3.9	4.0	5.2	5.3	3.3	4.4	2.47	2.9	3.3	5.1	3.4	3.97
8	Timely communication of planning decisions to resi- dents	4.6	5.1	3.9	2.1	3.9	3.6	5.2	5.2	2.8	4.2	2.72	2.9	3.2	5.1	3.5	3.91
9	Time lag before decision is taken	4.5	5.0	3.9	2.7	4.0	3.5	5.1	3.1	3.1	3.7	2.75	2.8	3.3	5.1	3.5	3.77
1	Timely action on contraven- tion	4.6	5.0	3.7	2.5	4.0	4.1	5.0	5.2	3.2	4.3	2.48	2.8	3.1	5.0	3.4	3.97
1	Politeness of the develop- ment control officer	4.3	4.8	3.7	2.7	3.9	4.0	5.1	5.3	2.6	4.3	2.54	2.8	5.2	5.2	3.9	4.07
	Total	52.06	58.58	41.52	27.08	44.79	42.38	57.00	53.39	31.75	46.14	28.40	30.68	38.07	57.78	38.83	43.26
		4.73	5.33	3.77	2.46	4.07	3.85	5.18	4.85	2.89	4.19	2.589	2.79	3.46	5.25	3.53	3.93

Source: Author's Field Survey updated, 2023

3.3.4 Residents' Level of Satisfaction with the Functions of Development Control Agencies in Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti and Osogbo

The level of satisfaction expressed by the respondents with the functions of development control agencies in the three cities is presented in Table 6. From

the Table, the mean \overline{RSI} for the three cities was 3.98 which indicated that respondents' perceptions were closer to just satisfied than dissatisfied. Further analysis however revealed that six of the identified functions of development control agencies had indices higher than the mean of RSI for the study area. These functions which include timely detection of contravention and politeness of the development control officer to developers with an index of 4.07 each of these enjoyed the highest level of satisfaction among the respondents. Others were the period of granting planning approval to a proposed development plan, dissemination and making available planning information to developers and timely communication of planning decisions to developers. Their respective indices were 3.97, 3.94 and 3.91.

3.4 Respondents' Perception of Problems of Development Control Agencies in the Study Area

The levels of seriousness of the challenges of development control were investigated from the perspective of respondents. The method of investigation followed the earlier methods used for determining the agency's functions and residents' satisfaction in this study. For this purpose, thirteen challenges were identified and respondents were asked to rate each using very much serious, very serious, serious, just serious, not serious, not very serious and not very much serious. Each of these was assigned a weight value of 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The responses from the respondents were developed into the Level of Seriousness Index (LSI). The index ranges between 7 and 1. The closer the index to seven, the higher is the seriousness of the problems of control agencies.

3.4.1 Residents Perceptions of Problems of Development Control Agencies in Abeokuta

The summary of responses to problems of development control is presented in Table 7. A careful observation of the result revealed that the problem perceived as most serious in the high residential density area of Abeokuta was the lack of a development plan for the city (4.89). This view is a confirmation of the fact that there was no Operative Development Plan to guide physical development activities in the city. The implication of this

is that physical development activities in the city will not be properly coordinated when not built on an effective development plan. Other problems considered to be of serious magnitude were political interference (4.56), bribery and corruption among workers of development control agencies (3.69), poor staff strength (3.47), poor monitoring of development activities (3.41), and poor funding (3.31).

In the medium density, six of the identified problems confronting development control were considered to be of serious magnitude. These were a lack of development plan, poor monitoring, poor funding, bribery and corruption, political interference, and poor staff strength. Their respective LSI were 4.93, 4.70, 4.52, 4.36, 4.26 and 3.56. Each of the remaining seven problems had an index below the mean of LSI for the zone.

With a mean index of 3.96 findings showed that eight of the identified problems of development control had indices higher than the mean of LSI in the low density. The problem perceived as most serious was poor funding of the development control agencies (5.43). Planning agencies need equipment especially means of transportation to and fro sites for effective monitoring. Where this is not available will hamper the effectiveness of development control operation. Other problems perceived as serious in the zone include political interference (5.28), lack of development/master plan (5.19), poor monitoring (4.75), bribery and corruption (4.07), inadequate tool and equipment (4.04) and poor staff strength (4.00).

Similar to what was established in the low density, poor funding was the most serious problem confronting development control in the planned residential scheme. Inadequate funding will no doubt hinder the agencies from meeting their financial obligations and consequently affect the effective discharge of their responsibilities. Other problems with positive deviations from the mean of LSI were political interference (5.32), poor monitoring (5.18), lack of development/master plan (5.07), poor staff strength (4.00), bribery and corruption (3.61) and inadequate tool and equipment (3.61).

Analysis of problems militating against the effectiveness of development control from the perspective of respondents in Abeokuta revealed that six of the identified problems had indices higher than the mean of LSI for the city. These problems were lack of development/master plan, political interference, poor funding, poor

monitoring, bribery and corruption among the workers and poor staff strength were the most prevailing problems of development control in the city. Their respective LSI (3.56) were 5.02, 4.86, 4.83, 4.50, 3.93 and 3.76.

3.4.2 Residents Perceptions of Problems of Development Control Agencies in Ado-Ekiti

In Ado-Ekiti, the problems identified as serious in the order of magnitude in the high density were delay in response to petitions (4.62), bribery and corruption among the workers of development control agencies (4.50), poor monitoring (4.47), overlapping of functions with other agencies (4.41), lack of development/master plan (4.31) and absence of effective and enabling law (4.20). Others were political interference and lack of cooperation from public members with an index of 4.12 each respectively.

Contrary to what was established in the high density, bribery and corruption among the workers (4.19) was the most serious problem of development control in the medium density. Other problems in order of seriousness in the zone were poor monitoring (4.14), delay in response to petitions (4.05), lack of cooperation from the public members (4.04), lack of development/master plans (4.02), absence of effective and enabling law (3.93), poor staff strength (3.84) and political interference (3.80).

In the low density of Ado-Ekiti, eight of the identified problems had positive deviations about the mean of LSI (3.86), while the remaining five problems had negative deviations from the mean. The most serious of these problems was poor monitoring of physical development activities (4.82).

Of the perceived problems in the planned residential scheme, the most serious in occurrence was political interference (4.93). Information obtained revealed that Ekiti State Housing Corporation sealed up houses of respondents who had not finished paying up their mortgage and those owing backlog of annual ground rent on the directive of the state government specifically in 2015. This could be the reason why political interference was perceived as the most serious problem of development control in the zone. Other problems considered to be of serious magnitude include lack of development/master plan (4.82), absence of effective and enabling law (4.64), delay in response to petitions (4.64), poor staff strength (4.25), inadequate tool and equipment (4.25) and poor funding (4.05).

The summary of the responses in Ado-Ekiti showed that eight of the identified problems of development control were of serious magnitude in the city. The most serious of these however was delay in response to petitions (4.49). Others in the order of importance were lack of development/master plan (4.44), absence of effective and enabling law (4.26), political interference (4.19), poor monitoring (4.17), bribery and corruption (4.01), poor staff strength (3.92) and inadequate tool and equipment (3.90).

3.4.3 Residents' Perception of the Problems of Development Control in Osogbo

From Table 7, seven of the identified problems of development control had indices higher than the mean of LSI for the high residential density of Osogbo. It was clear from the result of perceptions that it was not the number of planning workers that mattered but the quality. This could be the reason why respondents in the zone perceived a lack of experienced and qualified personnel (4.21) as the most serious problem of development control. Other problems identified in order of severity were bribery and corruption (4.19), absence of effective and enabling law (4.18), overlapping of functions with other agencies (4.10), lack of development/master plan (4.01), political interference (3.74) and poor funding (3.62).

In the medium density, the most serious problem from the point of view of respondents was the lack of development/master plans. Information obtained from the planning agencies in the city revealed that there was no master plan prepared to guide development activities in the city. The absence of development plans for the city will no doubt lead to haphazard development. Other problems with positive deviations about the mean of LSI (3.69) include inadequate tools and equipment (4.03), bribery and corruption (4.02), delay in response to petitions (3.98), and overlapping of function with other agencies (3.89).

The most severe problem perceived in the low density of Osogbo as shown in the Table was poor monitoring of development control activities (4.34). There were lots of new developments ongoing in the low residential density area. This reason for this can not be divorced from the fact that there were large numbers of vacant plots for development in the area. Where these developments are not properly monitored, developers may deviate from the approved development plans and in consequence lead to haphazard development. Other problems militating against the activities of development control in

the order of severity were lack of development/master plan (4.08), absence of effective and enabling law (3.73), political interference (3.69), delay in response to petitions (3.66), bribery and corruption (3.49) and lack of experience and qualified personnel (3.46).

In the planned residential scheme, all the problems identified except inadequate tools and equipment (3.11) had positive deviations from the mean of LSI. Some of the problems identified in the zone include delay in response to petitions, poor monitoring, lack of development/master plan, and absence of effective and enabling law. Their respective deviations were 1.06, 0.95, 0.71 and 0.06.

In Osogbo, the most serious problem of development control was poor monitoring of physical development activities with an index of 4.15. Other problems with positive deviations were lack of development/master plan (4.12), absence of effective and enabling law (4.03), overlapping of functions with other agencies (3.89), delay in response to petitions (3.85), bribery and corruption (3.80), political interference (3.76) and lack of qualified personnel (3.74).

3.4.4 Respondents' Perception of the Problems of Development Control in Abeokuta, Ado-Ekiti and Osogbo

The combined result of the perception of problems confronting development control in the three cities show that the mean LSI for the study area was 3.06. This implies that the respondents' perceptions of the level of seriousness of development control problems were closer to dissatisfied than just satisfied. Findings reveal that six identified problems had positive deviations from the mean of LSI. These include lack of development/master plan, poor monitoring, political interference, bribery and corruption, poor funding, and delay in response to petitions. Their respective indices were 4.57, 4.28, 4.27, 3.91, 3.86 and 3.76. Of these six most serious challenges, only bribery corruption and lack of development plan had positive deviations across all the residential densities in the study area. This indicates that the most pressing challenges of development control in the study area are bribery corruption and lack of development plans to channel growth and development in the study area.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study has examined residents' perception of development activities in cities of Southwestern Nigeria. The findings established a variation in the socio-economic characteristics of residents across the residential zones. This indicates that people of different socio-economic characteristics occupy different residential areas in the city. For example, the study reveals that the high-density residential zone accommodated the highest proportion of residents whose ages were above 60 years (55.9%); residents without formal education (45.7%), and residents whose monthly income was less than the national minimum wage of N35,000 (14.2%) as at the time when this study was conducted. These proportions were reduced as distance increases from the high to low residential density. On the other hand, the core area (high density) sheltered the majority (50.5%) of residents who have stayed longer than 30 years, which varies inversely with distance to the low-density residential area. The findings from the study further demonstrated that socioeconomic characteristics influence the residents' perception of development control activities in the study area. Findings from this study reveal that residents' perceptions of the functions of development control agencies were low in the study area. The result further indicates that residents in the high residential density exhibited the lowest level of understanding of the roles of the planning agencies.

Similarly, the resident's level of satisfaction with functions performed by the planning agencies in the study area was low. The study established that residents of Osogbo expressed the lowest satisfaction level, this was higher in Abeokuta but highest in Ado-Ekiti. The study further confirmed that development control operations face several challenges that vary across the residential densities. It was discovered that despite the differences in the opinion expressed by residents regarding the problems confronting development control in the study area, consensus exists that two major issues are common to all the planning agencies in the cities of the Southwestern region. These are a lack of development/master plan and bribery and corruption. This implies that no operative development plans were in place to channel the city's growth and development, resulting in incompatible land uses and haphazard development. Corruption among the planning officials compromises the planning regulations and inefficiency in develop-

ment control implementation.

Based on the above, the following are recommended to ensure efficient development control implementation and sustainable urban development in the cities.

- i. There is a need for aggressive public education and enlightenment campaigns to sensitize and arouse the consciousness of residents about the activities of planning and development control agencies, especially in the high and medium residential density where understanding and awareness are low. This can be done through television and radio programs/jingles, social media, religious bodies, seminars
- ii. During development control implementation, special attention should be paid to the specific needs of the people in different residential areas. There is a need for proper domestication of the National Urban and Regional Planning Law of 1992 in each state. During public hearings, the prevailing social, physical, economic, and environmental peculiarities would be integrated into the law. This will increase the level of acceptability and legitimacy of the planning and development control operations among the residents.
- iii. There is a need for training and re-training of planning officials on how to adopt global best practices while discharging their official duties. This will help them to benchmark the performance, identify gaps, and improve the outcomes.
- iv. Efforts should be made to adopt technology in processing development plan approval. This will reduce face-to-face contact between the prospective applicants and the planning officials and to a large extent curb corruption. In addition, the government must be decisive in fighting corruption in the planning agencies. The corrupt officials should be identified and appropriate sanctions should be meted out against them. This will no doubt boost the trust of the residents in the development control process and their compliance with planning regulations.

It is clear based on the outcome of this study that part of the reason why haphazard development pervades cities in the southwestern region of Nigeria is the lack of development plans to guide the growth and development of these settlements. The planning officials in the agencies in cities of Southwestern Nigeria should as a matter of urgency set in motion the process for the preparation of development plans as outlined in sections 13-26 of the Nigerian Urban and Regional Planning Law of 1992. Efforts

should be made to involve the people in the conception, preparation, and implementation of the development plans as this will enhance the success of development control operations in the region. across the residential densities. It was discovered that despite the differences in the opinion expressed by residents regarding the problems confronting development control in the study area, consensus exists that two major issues are common to all the planning agencies in the cities of the Southwestern region. These are a lack of development/master plan and bribery and corruption. This implies that no operative development plans were in place to channel the city's growth and development, resulting in incompatible land uses and haphazard development. Corruption among the planning officials compromises the planning regulations and inefficiency in development control implementation.

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Table 7: Residents' Perception of Level of Seriousness of Development Control Problems in Abeokuta, Ado – Ekiti and Osogbo

The problem of Development Control	Abeokuta			Ado-Ekiti			Osogbo			Three Cities Total						
	Highest	Medium	Low	Highest	Medium	Low	Highest	Medium	Low							
1 Bribery and corruption	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI	LSI						
2 Poor staff strength	3.69	4.36	4.07	3.61	3.93	4.50	4.19	3.97	3.39	4.01	4.19	4.02	3.49	3.48	3.80	3.91
3 Inadequate tool and equipment	3.47	3.56	4.00	4.00	3.76	3.79	3.84	3.80	4.25	3.92	2.70	3.84	2.77	3.54	3.21	3.63
4 Political interference	2.96	3.26	4.04	3.61	3.47	3.71	3.54	4.10	4.25	3.90	2.76	4.03	2.90	3.11	3.20	3.52
5 Overlapping function with other agencies	4.56	4.26	5.28	5.32	4.86	4.12	3.80	3.89	4.93	4.19	3.74	3.76	3.69	3.83	3.76	4.27
6 Lack of experienced and qualified personnel	2.59	2.63	2.90	2.21	2.58	4.41	3.35	3.12	3.68	3.64	4.10	3.85	3.65	3.94	3.89	3.37
7 Absence of effective and enabling law	2.70	2.54	3.17	2.21	2.66	3.99	3.33	3.05	2.43	3.20	4.21	3.49	3.46	3.79	3.74	3.20
8 Lack of cooperation from the public member	2.67	2.51	3.01	2.07	2.56	4.20	3.93	4.25	4.64	4.26	4.18	4.19	3.73	4.02	4.03	3.62
9 Poor funding	2.70	2.56	3.03	2.14	2.61	4.12	4.04	3.15	2.89	3.55	3.48	3.15	3.23	3.81	3.42	3.19
1 Inadequate office accommodation	3.31	4.52	5.43	6.04	4.83	3.39	3.29	3.36	4.07	3.53	3.62	3.09	2.67	3.52	3.23	3.86
0 Lack of development/master plan	2.79	2.46	3.05	2.11	2.60	3.65	3.60	3.45	3.04	3.44	3.06	3.09	3.08	3.83	3.27	3.10
1 Poor monitoring	4.89	4.93	5.19	5.07	5.02	4.31	4.02	4.60	4.82	4.44	4.01	3.73	4.08	4.67	4.12	4.53
2 Delay in response to petitions	3.41	4.70	4.75	5.18	4.50	4.47	4.14	4.82	3.25	4.17	3.55	3.78	4.34	4.91	4.15	4.28
3 Total	3.06	2.83	3.53	2.32	2.94	4.62	4.05	4.65	4.64	4.49	2.73	3.98	3.66	5.02	3.85	3.76
LSI	42.8	45.1	51.4	45.8	46.3	53.1	49.1	50.2	50.2	50.7	46.3	48.0	44.7	51.4	46.6	48.24
	2	3	9	3	3	9	2	1	8	4	3	0	5	7	7	7
	3.29	3.47	3.96	3.53	4.09	3.78	3.86	3.87	3.90	3.56	3.69	3.44	3.48	3.59	3.71	3.56

Source: Author' Field Survey , 2023

- iii There is a need for training and re-training of planning officials on how to adopt global best practices while discharging their official duties. This will help them to benchmark the performance, identify gaps, and improve the outcomes.
- iv Efforts should be made to adopt technology in processing development plan approval. This will reduce face-to-face contact between the prospective applicants and the planning officials and to a large extent curb corruption. In addition, the government must be decisive in fighting corruption in the planning agencies. The corrupt officials should be identified and appropriate sanctions should be meted out against them. This will no doubt boost the trust of the residents in the development control process and their compliance with planning regulations.

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